

Problems in Microservice Development

* Indicates required question

1. How many years have you worked in software development? *

2. How many years have you worked in microservice development? *

3. What roles have you had in your team during microservice development? *

4. What development work do you do in relation to microservices? *

Check all that apply.

Backend Implementation (programming)

API Development

Documentation

Orchestration

Deployment

Architecture Design

Other: _____

You will now be asked to rate a series of problems against the impact they have on your development time and the frequency you find yourself needing to solve these problems.

Be aware that some problems may simply not apply to your prior experience (e.g. questions pertaining to multi-broker architectures) in these cases please do not answer the question.

The problems are split into multiple pages based on their subject matter.

This is primarily for organisational purposes, do not worry too much about the names.

After each set of problems you will be asked to enter any additional problems you have that are not included in the survey. Please do not hesitate to include any problem, no matter how similar it is to one already listed. Again, do not worry too much about the specific category names.

Glossary

Pub/Sub - A communication architecture where microservices publish and subscribe to messages from specific channels rather than messaging each other directly.

RESTful - A communication architecture where microservices communicate directly over HTTP requests.

Channel - also called topics. Microservices publish or subscribe to messages from specific channels in Pub/Sub architectures.

Message broker - you may also know this as a message bus. The application that handles the routing and forwarding of messages between microservices.

Topology Problems

5. For the following problems, please rate what impact they have on your development time.

Mark only one oval per row.

	No Impact	Small Impact	Moderate Impact	Large Impact	Massive Impact
What microservices are sending messages to this microservice?	<input type="radio"/>				
What microservices are receiving messages from this microservice?	<input type="radio"/>				
What channels is this microservice published/subscribed to?	<input type="radio"/>				
What microservices publish/subscribe to this channel?	<input type="radio"/>				
What message brokers is this microservice communicating with?	<input type="radio"/>				
What message brokers is this message broker communicating with? (for multi-broker architectures)	<input type="radio"/>				
What is the shortest communication path between two microservices?	<input type="radio"/>				
What type of communication is this microservice using? (pub/sub, REST, etc)	<input type="radio"/>				

7. Do you have any other topology related problems?
Include what impact do they have, and how frequently do you need to solve them.

Deployment Problems

8. For the following problems, please rate what impact they have on your development time.

Mark only one oval per row.

	No Impact	Small Impact	Moderate Impact	Large Impact	Massive Impact
What host/hardware is this microservice running on?	<input type="radio"/>				
What microservices are running on this host/hardware?	<input type="radio"/>				
How many instances of this microservice are running at any one time?	<input type="radio"/>				

9. How frequently do you need to solve the following problems?

Mark only one oval per row.

	Daily	Weekly	Monthly	Quarterly	Yearly or Less	Never
What host/hardware is this microservice running on?	<input type="radio"/>					
What microservices are running on this host/hardware?	<input type="radio"/>					
How many instances of this microservice are running at any one time?	<input type="radio"/>					

10. Do you have any other deployment related problems?
Include what impact do they have, and how frequently do you need to solve them.

Glossary

Channel - also called topics. Microservices publish or subscribe to messages from specific channels in Pub/Sub architectures.

Microservice type - some projects group or design their microservices to fit into certain categories, such as functional, infrastructural, web server, database, etc.

Data Problems

11. For the following problems, please rate what impact they have on your development time.

Mark only one oval per row.

	No Impact	Small Impact	Moderate Impact	Large Impact	Massive Impact
What microservices use this data structure?	<input type="radio"/>				
What is the data structure of messages in this channel?	<input type="radio"/>				
How is the channel string structured? (e.g. is '/temp/room1' static, or is 'room1' dynamic for different sensors?)	<input type="radio"/>				
What is the purpose of this microservice?	<input type="radio"/>				
What is the purpose of this channel?	<input type="radio"/>				
What type of microservice is this?	<input type="radio"/>				

13. Do you have any other data related problems?
Include what impact do they have, and how frequently do you need to solve them.

Development Problems

14. For the following problems, please rate what impact they have on your development time.

Mark only one oval per row.

	No Impact	Small Impact	Moderate Impact	Large Impact	Massive Impact
Who maintains this microservice?	<input type="radio"/>				
What microservices does this person/team maintain?	<input type="radio"/>				
What languages/libraries does this microservice use?	<input type="radio"/>				

15. How frequently do you need to solve the following problems?

Mark only one oval per row.

	Daily	Weekly	Monthly	Quarterly	Yearly or Less	Never
Who maintains this microservice?	<input type="radio"/>					
What microservices does this person/team maintain?	<input type="radio"/>					
What languages/libraries does this microservice use?	<input type="radio"/>					

16. Do you have any other development related problems?

Include what impact do they have, and how frequently do you need to solve them.

Scenario Problems

17. For the following problems, please rate what impact they have on your development time.

Mark only one oval per row.

	No Impact	Small Impact	Moderate Impact	Large Impact	Massive Impact
If this microservice goes down what other microservices will be affected?	<input type="radio"/>				
If this message broker goes down what microservices will be affected?	<input type="radio"/>				
If this microservice is not functioning correctly what other microservices could be the cause?	<input type="radio"/>				

18. How frequently do you need to solve the following problems?

Mark only one oval per row.

	Daily	Weekly	Monthly	Quarterly	Yearly or Less	Never
If this microservice goes down what other microservices will be affected?	<input type="radio"/>					
If this message broker goes down what microservices will be affected?	<input type="radio"/>					
If this microservice is not functioning correctly what other microservices could be the cause?	<input type="radio"/>					

19. Do you have any other scenario related problems?

Include what impact do they have, and how frequently do you need to solve them.

Other

20. Do you have any other microservice related problems?
Include what impact do they have, and how frequently do you need to solve them.

Glossary

Documentation tool - any resource that presents information about the microservice architecture you are working on. This can include text-based documentation, visual graphs, interactive software, system logs, etc.

21. What existing documentation tools do you use? *
Please state what you use them for, how frequently you use them, and how useful you find them.

22. What would be your ideal documentation tool?

By submitting you are giving consent for your response to be used in this study in accordance with the information sheet provided on page 1 of this survey.

You will not be able to change, withdraw, or resubmit your answers after submission.

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